

Paper 3

INNOVATIVE PRACTICES IN PEDAGOGY
Topic: CONSTRUCTIVIST PEDAGOGY FOR NEXT-GEN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The growth and development of a country, by and large depends on the quality of education offered to students. The quality of education in turn depends on the effective planning and execution of four integral aspects of education viz., Formulating Value-Based Aims and Objectives; Developing a Reflective, Need-Based and Context-Relevant Curriculum; Employing Effective Teaching Strategies and Creating Learning Contexts in schools and colleges; and improvising most Objective Techniques and Tools of Evaluation.

It is indeed a sorry state of affairs that even today teaching is just transacting curriculum by way of direct explanation of the content for conceptual understanding by students where students are just passive recipients of information rather active producers of new knowledge. In the context of NCF 2005, which strongly advocates self-construction of knowledge, it is very significant to rethink about the dynamics of curricular transaction and redesign the pedagogic dimensions so as to enable students construct their own knowledge, relate it to the immediate environment, reflect it in their personality and extend the same for problem solving in life and community for a better quality of life. More specifically learning needs to be shifted from passive and conventional methods to active and innovative methods.

In this context one has to seriously think about how to make children active learners with an enhanced ability to construct their own knowledge and become productive citizens of our country. There is an element of discovery, exploration, and inquiry in every child that probably lead him or her to a contributory individual. In a nutshell each individual student is a budding scientist. Pull out that scientist from each student. This would be possible only when we modify our information transferring conventional classrooms into a place where new knowledge is produced, skills are sharpened, attitude is positively shifted, aptitude is magnified and in total the competence levels of students are boosted up. This indeed requires a new pedagogy called constructivistic pedagogy employed in constructivist

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classroom contexts.

This article is an attempt to throw light on sensitizing the teachers with regard to refine their understanding of their constructivist roles and transform into facilitators of active-self-learning among students. It is titled, “Constructivist Pedagogy for Next-Gen Students.”

Introduction:

Effective Teaching and meaningful Learning are the two foci of imparting productive education. If both are to be highly qualitative, it's very important for the teachers and practitioners to realise and refine their understandings of curriculum transaction. It is an accepted fact that effective teachers are usually not born but made through training, exposure and experience. Good teachers nurture their knowledge and skills through constant and deliberate efforts. One of the prerequisite to be a good teacher is to understand the teaching-learning process and effective classroom management in more depth.

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In this context one has to seriously think about how to make children active learners with an enhanced ability to construct their own knowledge and become productive citizens of our country. There is an element of discovery, exploration, and inquiry in every child that probably lead him or her to a contributory individual. In a nutshell each individual student is a budding scientist. Pull out that scientist from each student. This would be possible only when teachers modify their information transferring conventional classrooms into a place where new knowledge is produced, skills are sharpened, attitude is positively shifted, aptitude is magnified and in total

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the competence levels of students are boosted up. This indeed requires a new pedagogy called **constructivistic pedagogy**. Teachers shall try to refine and reflect their understandings of the principles of constructivism and put conscious efforts to design a **constructivist learning environment** in classrooms called **constructivist classrooms** in their day to day teaching.

Constructivism

The passive view of teaching views the learner as ‘an empty vessel’ to be filled with knowledge, whereas constructivism states that learners construct meaning only through active engagement with the world (such as experiments or real-world problem solving). Information may be passively received, but understanding cannot be, for it must come from making meaningful connections between prior knowledge, new knowledge, and the processes involved in learning.

Constructivism is ‘an approach to learning that holds that people actively construct or make their own knowledge and that reality is determined by the experiences of the learner’ (Elliott et al., 2000)

The central idea of Constructivism is that human learning is constructed and that learners build new knowledge upon the foundation of previous knowledge. This prior knowledge influences what new or modified knowledge an individual will construct from new learning experiences. (Phillips, 1995).

Constructive Pedagogy:

Any teaching strategy or approach that is based on the theory of constructivism. This pedagogy is widely accepted as a basis for thinking about teaching and learning. Constructivist teaching is about making good learners as opposed to simply giving information to students. Constructive pedagogy involves shifts between teachers intervening with proposition of new ideas in terms of exposition and students’ engagement with individual or group activities that may be student-centered but teacher directed. It is not the name of a particular single teaching approach or strategy. It conglomerates a wide variety of teaching-learning approaches that ultimately lead to self-construction of knowledge by students. In a constructivist classroom, teacher intends to have his students explore concepts in an organic way focusing on teaching students how to learn, instead of just giving them information about facts

Theory and Principles underlying Constructive Pedagogy:

Learning is the process of modification in the behaviour of an individual. Its reflected in acquiring new understanding, knowledge, skills, values, attitudes and aptitude. Learning occurs through responses given by students to given stimuli. Some learning is immediate, induced by a single event but skills and knowledge accumulate from repeated experiences. Learning is active, build on prior knowledge, occurs in a complex social environment, and requires learner’s motivation and cognitive engagement with an authentic context.

Active learning is student-centered learning, which occurs when a student interacts with his/her learning experience. Since understanding the information is the key aspect of learning, it is important for learners to recognize what they understand and what they do not. By doing so, they can monitor their own mastery of subjects. Active learning encourages learners to have an internal dialogue in which they verbalize understandings. Conversely, passive learning and direct instruction are characteristics of teacher-centered learning often considered as conventional teaching.

Meaningful learning is that the acquired knowledge is fully understood to the extent that it relates to other knowledge. To this end, meaningful learning contrasts with rote learning in which information is acquired without regard to understanding. Meaningful learning, on the other hand, implies there is a comprehensive knowledge of the context of the facts learned or concept developed.

Constructivist learning theory underpins a variety of student-centered teaching methods and techniques which contrast with conventional methods, whereby knowledge in terms of information is passively transmitted by teachers to students. By and large constructivistic pedagogy is grounded on the propositions made by **Jean Piaget, Lev Vygotsky, Ernst Von Glasersfeld** and others in their learning theories such as Learning is a cognitive process where students learn through thinking on trial and error bases; Students learn through new experiences in comparison with the existing ones; learning contexts shall be designed in par with the four stages of learning (Sensorimotor – Preoperational – Concrete and Formal Operation) as biological development of the child is central to learning; and students learn better on their own through social interaction – in fact this leads even to the promotion of 21st century skills like Collaboration, Communication,

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Cooperation, Creative thinking and Critical thinking.

Knowledge can only exist within the human mind, and that it does not have to match any real world reality (Driscoll, 2000). The constructivist theory posits that Learning exist in the mind; Learners will be constantly trying to develop their own individual mental model of the real world from their perceptions of that world. As they perceive each new experience, learners will continually update their own mental models to reflect the new information, and will, therefore, construct their own interpretation of reality.

Constructivist pedagogy follows five major principles viz. Students’ points of view are sought and valued; Designing such classroom activities that challenge student assumptions; 3. Teachers pose relevant problems; Minor or subsuming concepts are developed around the major concepts; and Assessment of learning attainment is done contextually and continuously.

Powered with Stuff to Empower Learners for Active Learning:

Constructive Pedagogy perceives the student as an active self-constructor of knowledge but not a passive recipient of information; It designs new and challenging activities to ignite thinking, analyzing, reasoning and applying; It enables students connecting their newly constructed knowledge to life outside the school; Learning is shifted away from rote methods; Curriculum transacted goes beyond text book; evaluation is continuous, comprehensive, more flexible and non-threatening; and democratic values like equality, justice, secularism, freedom of thought and expression etc. are integrated; No constraints such as gender, class, creed; highly experiential, interactive with more scope for students expression.

Constructivist Teacher – An extreme Facilitator

While employing the constructive pedagogy in classes, teachers shall perceive themselves as extreme facilitators and are expected to play their role to the core. Any constructivist strategy, technique or approach they employ shall give optimum scope for, knowledge construction by students and not knowledge reproduction; providing multiple representations of reality; emphasizing authentic tasks in a meaningful context rather than abstract instruction out of context; motivating students for thoughtful reflection on their classroom learning experiences; experiential learning and not conventional teaching; extended learner autonomy and initiative; encouraging

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inquiry among students; nurturing learners natural inquisitiveness; taking into account the learner’s mental model at optimum; involving learners in real world situations; supporting co-operative learning; and in total learning should be a joyful experience of self-construction of knowledge.

Added to these, teachers when employ constructive pedagogy shall create a collaborative problem-solving environment where students become active participants in their own learning; engage students in experiences that challenge previous conceptions of their existing knowledge; allow student responses to drive the lessons and seek elaborations of students’ initial responses; give more opportunities and time for students thinking for hypothesizing and testing the same or posing relevant questions by asking thoughtful and open-ended questions; encourage thoughtful and focused discussions among students; construct activities or frame tasks such as ‘classifying’, ‘analyzing’, and ‘creating’ etc.; encourage and accept student autonomy and initiative; it does not matter to be willing to let go of classroom control; insist on clear expression from students as they need to learn to communicate or explain what they have explored; promote student leadership, collaboration, location of information and problem solving as a product of learning; encourage using alternate sources for information both from written materials and experts; encourage students to challenge each other’s conceptualizations in a healthy way and ultimately there shall be unity shifted from chaotic diversity.

An Illustrative model of Constructivist Learning – 5 Es Model:

In this regard, One of the most popular and quiet often used instructional model based on constructivist theory, **Five E’s (5Es) model**, was developed by **Roger Bybee**. This model for implementing constructivism in the classroom suggests that constructivists’ lessons should engage students, allow them to explore, aid them in explaining their experience, learning is elaborated, and the lesson includes evaluation. The dynamics of learning in this model is pivoted on active participation of students through continuous interaction with peer members, with learning context and of course with the teacher too, who is a facilitator. This enterprise percolates and cuts across five identified and labelled integral dimensions of constructivist learning viz. **Engage – Explore – Explain – Elaborate – Evaluate**. Several instructional strategies are evolved using this model.

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Engaging students: Facilitating learning environment, learning activities and situations and focusing the minds of learners on the higher order learning tasks. Engaging learners can be done through asking open ended questions; acting out a problematic situation; defining a problem; showing a surprising event; Noting down an unexpected phenomena; considering possible responses to questions; and Presenting situations where student’s perceptions vary.

Exploring by students: Learners are guided to explore and find answers for the questions/issues raised during the engage stage. Teachers’ role is to structure and present learning environment which facilitates learners to involve in investigative activities and provide opportunities for students to get directly involved with discovery process and construction of knowledge. This could be done by, providing structured activities; giving work in teams; experimenting with materials; using pupils’ inquiry to drive the process; employing problem solving strategies; identifying sequence or patterns of events; brainstorming possible alternatives; etc. According to constructivist approaches, it is very suitable to structure small groups while involving in the above mentioned activities or any appropriate activity. Cooperative learning strategies are most suitable for this purpose.

Explaining by students: Earlier students were engaged in the learning activities and through mutual interactions discovered or constructed new knowledge and they should be given opportunities for expressing this abstract knowledge through communicable form. Students can express the constructed knowledge in different ways like, explaining the constructed ideas in their own way; constructing and explaining a model; reviewing and criticizing solutions; representing ideas through pictures/figures/graphs; representing information through symbols; presenting a summary based on the data; presenting the data through patterns; present oral and written reports, etc.

Extension of Knowledge by students: Students are provided with opportunities and guidance by teacher to apply the constructed knowledge in several real life situations or for problem solving. The students can also correlate the newly constructed knowledge to other related fields of knowledge. These new relationships can further lead to new discoveries or new understandings. This is done by way of applying knowledge and skills in real life situations; transferring of knowledge and skills; sharing information and ideas; developing products and promote ideas; ask

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new questions etc.

Evaluation by teacher: Teacher evaluates whether the students have constructed the knowledge completely and correctly, and also whether they have developed conceptual understandings. According to constructivist theory, evaluation should be as far as possible diagnostic in nature. Teacher can use, Checklists for observation, Projects and problem based learning products, Achievement tests, Concept/mind mappings, Portfolio assessments, Performance assessments, Rubrics, Student interviews etc.

Conclusion:

High knowledge explosion is a predominant feature of the 21st century. The new world witnesses a huge population of new generation of students who live in knowledge and skill driven society and who are hungry of higher level knowledge and skills. It's high time to anticipate the academic requirements of the next-gen students, who will definitely have enormous urge and instincts for knowledge and skills added with high achievement motivation. It is indeed becoming a growing challenge for teachers to manage the hyper inquisitive learners of the present world in their schools and classrooms. If teaching becomes dry and drab with the same conventional method and approaches, it's sure that this new generation learners may get disappointed, loose interest, get demotivated and move away from teachers and formal schooling. So it's the ethically bound duty of teachers to rediscover themselves and employ innovative strategies and approaches. This needs to be immediately addressed and attention has to be on making classrooms and schools-the epicenters of knowledge explosion. Constructivist pedagogy would definitely empower the teachers with constructivist competencies that fulfil the learning needs of the next-gen students.

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